

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15015585

Improving Dyscalculia In Junior Secondary School Students' Performances In Mathematics Through Behaviour Modification In Sokoto State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study will investigate the Dyscalculia Junior Secondary School Students (JSS 3) Performances in Mathematics through Behaviour Modification in Sokoto metropolis in Sokoto State. A total of twelve thousand, eight hundred and eighty-six (12,886) forms the population of the study with three thousand, two hundred and twenty-four (3,224) students were sampled. Proportionate sampling technique was used to select three hundred and forty-one (341) JSS 3 students with ninety-six (96) dyscalculia and two hundred and forty-five (245) normal students which was in line with Roscoe (1975) who state that “a sample size of more than 30 and less 500 is considered appropriate for most research. So also, the researchers used table for determining the sample size (Krejcie and Morgan, 1970) to get the representative of the sample size. Also, Quasi experimental research design with pre-test and post-test were adopted in the study. The instrument adopted for the study was Dyscalculic Mathematics Test (DMT) developed by the researchers with 30 multiple choice objective questions. Descriptive statistics was used to answer research questions and t-tests was used to analyzed the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significant. The content validity of the test items was validated by the experts in Mathematics education measurement and evaluation. While reliability index using PPMC was used to estimate 0.86 as the reliability coefficient.

Keywords: Behaviour Modification, Dyscalculia, Mathematics, students

INTRODUCTION

Dyscalculia has its origins from the Greek words ‘dys’ and the Latin ‘calcularre’, meaning a difficulty in calculation, in applying Mathematics acquirements (Ferraz and Neves, (2015). Learners with dyscalculia are known to have a delay in their general Mathematics achievement level (Hoof, Verschaffel, Ghesquiere, and Dooren, 2017). A person is dyscalculic if his or her performance on an assessment is in the bottom 5% relative to a population (Finesilver and Rodd, 2017). In this study, dyscalculic students are the students who achieved 5% bottom among the population in their Mathematics assessment. Although an etiological understanding of dyscalculia is still undetermined, numerous studies have attempted to find some possible causes. Some studies claims that dyscalculia is hereditary, is gaining support in the cognitive sciences (Ansari & Karmiloff-Smith, 2002), because the mathematical learning disorder is unusually common in identical twins and, to a lesser degree, fraternal twins and other siblings (Shalev, Manor, Kerem, Ayali, Badichi, Friedlander & Gross-Tsur, 2001). Other researches have been less successful in formulating whether there is a biological malady within the brain that specifically causes dyscalculia.

Mathematical skills are fundamental to independent living in a numerate society, affecting educational opportunities, employment opportunities and thus socio-economic status (Geary, 2004). An understanding of how concepts of numeracy develop, and the manifestation of difficulties in the acquisition of such concepts and skills, is crucial. For many children, Mathematics is an inherently difficult subject to learn. Between 5 and 8 percent of children between the ages of 6 and 14 have a particular type of cognitive deficiency that limits their aptitude to acquire knowledge and understanding of fundamental ideas in numeracy (Geary, 2004). Mathematics as the major area of difficulty for many youngsters with Learning disabilities.

Learning disabilities in Mathematics may be classified in at least three different groupings. One of these groups is characterized by an overall deficiency in Mathematics such that progress is slow and labored, but steady. A second group displays deficiencies in specific mathematics topics such as fractions, or within a subtopic such as division. A third group is characterized by comprehensive disorders of thinking, reasoning and problem solving such that performance in both concepts and skills in mathematics is bizarre, distorted and illogical. A severe mathematics learning disability and related conceptual disturbances in learning quantitative elements are sometimes referred to as dyscalculia (Ansari & Karmiloff-Smith, 2002). Dyscalculia has a medical connotation suggesting a central nervous system involvement. Increasingly, researchers in the cognitive sciences are studying this deficiency under the name dyscalculia, a disorder in which normally intelligent children demonstrate specific disabilities in learning mathematics (Ansari & Karmiloff-Smith, 2002). Teachers need to be informed about dyscalculia so that they can implement strategies that intentionally and explicitly accommodate students who have this disorder.

According to Santrock (2000), He discovered difficulties with Mathematical concepts, term and symbols arise from the realm of Mathematical thinking. While Talcott (2006) opines several variables ranging from the learners themselves, the teachers, the textbooks, the curricula, school environment to have been responsible for students' poor achievement in school Mathematics. Therefore, a successful teacher should always be prepared to assess the students' abilities, values and levels of difficulties and disabilities so as to make the necessary adjustment in remedial teaching. The level of students' performance in Mathematics determines the level of her/his difficulties in learning. For instance, if a student's score in Mathematics is very low, it indicates the level of his/her learning difficulty in the subject. Behaviour according to Santrock (2000) is everything we do that can be directly observed. While Colman (2003) views behaviour as the physical activity of an organism, including overt bodily movements and internal glandular and other physiological processes, constituting the sum total of the organism's physical responses to its environment. The term also denotes the specific physical responses of an organism to particular stimuli or classes of stimuli.

Statement of the Problem

The persistent poor or low performance in Mathematics in Junior Secondary School 3 students in terminal examinations and Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE) in Sokoto State, Nigeria has been a major concern for teachers, parents, educators, schools and Government who spent a lot of time and money in funding education but to no avail. The problems comprises negative attitude towards Mathematics, fear and anxiety towards Mathematics, inadequate qualified Mathematics teachers, poor teaching methods, lack of coverage, inadequate teaching materials, overcrowded classes, lack of good background form primary level, abstract in nature of the subject, difficult to be comprehended, boring, blaming the curriculum, Mathematics teachers and methods of teaching rather than student's lack of capacity to learn. The selection of teaching technique is not an easy task. This is because there are many methods that seems to work well for everyone and all situations. In addition, every Mathematics teacher should identify appropriate methodology based on the nature of the subject matter and instruction to be given. Most Mathematics teachers use irrelevant and ineffective methods of teaching which are among other factors contributing to students' poor performance in Mathematics which leads to not having good results in Mathematics in general.

Consistently, some students or pupils cannot identify individual numbers talk less of doing addition, subtraction, multiplication, divisions and identification of shapes. Virtually, students suffer skills and abilities needed in these basic Mathematical operations. Despite all these difficulties for both normal students and those with Mathematical problems, the poor performance of students in Mathematics has continued to surface in their internal examinations, Mathematical Competitions (Quiz and Olympiad) and common entrance examinations in Sokoto and Nigeria in general. But with adequate qualified Mathematics teachers at primary school level, adequate teaching materials and with good condition of learning environments; the poor performance of Mathematics at JSS level will reduce especially during terminal and external examinations to its maximum level. For effective teaching to take place a skillful Mathematics teacher needs to adapt many different strategies of teaching. Also, the study will therefore attempt to explore avenues through which teaching of Mathematics in Sokoto state can be made effective through JETS clubs and societies, attending quiz competitions among students, learning of Mathematics thought Internets and televisions will improve their performances towards Mathematics.

Objectives of the Study

The main objectives of this study were:

1. to find out the difference in performance between the students with Dyscalculia and normal students in Mathematics in Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto state.
2. to identify the difference in performance between Male and Female students with Dyscalculia in Mathematics in Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto state?

Research Questions

The study was therefore designed to seek answers to the following questions:

1. Is there any difference in performance between the students with Dyscalculia and normal students in Mathematics in Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto state?
2. Is there any difference in performance between Male and Female students with Dyscalculia in Mathematics in Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto state?

Research Hypotheses

The null hypotheses developed for the study includes:

HO_1 . There is no significant difference in performance between the students with Dyscalculia and normal students in Mathematics in Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto state?

HO_2 . There is no significant difference in performance between Male and Female students with Dyscalculia in Mathematics in Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto state?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study will employ quasi-experimental design using pre-test and post-test to experimental and control groups of Junior Secondary School students in Sokoto State, Nigeria. Questions will be administered from new general Mathematics text books and BECE past question papers. The researcher will conduct a survey to find out the schools and the students that will be involved in the study.

EG: O1 _____ X _____ O2

CG: O1 _____ X0 _____ O2

Research Design

Key:

EG: Experimental Group

CG: Control Group

O1: Pre-test

O2: Post test

X1: Treatment

X2: No treatment

Population of the Study

All Junior Secondary School (JSS 3) students in Sokoto metropolis in Sokoto State, Nigeria was involved in the study with an estimated population of twelve thousand eight hundred and eighty-six (12,886) under the Ministry for Basic and Secondary Education, Sokoto. Public schools were chosen to be the target audience for the study which were found to have difficulties in learning Mathematics (dyscalculia). Six junior secondary schools with population three thousand, two hundred and twenty-four (3,224) students were sampled.

Sample and sampling Techniques

From the survey conducted by the researchers, only Ninety-six (96) students were considered as dyscalculia and two hundred and forty-five (245) students were considered as students without dyscalculia (normal). Therefore, the sample of all the junior secondary school students were taken which was in accordance with Fox (1969) on purposeful sampling technique. The test results of Junior Secondary School students 3 were used from the selected schools. The last 15 – 20 JSS 3 students from the test list were purposefully selected which was also in accordance with Fox (1969). Proportionate method was employed to determine the sample size using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table for determining sample size from a given population. This is to enable the researchers obtain homogeneity in gender. in order to get the representative of the sample size. Hence, a sample of three hundred and forty-one (341) JSS 3 students were sampled and used for the study.

Instrument

The research instrument was employed in the study. The instrument provided information about Dyscalculic Mathematics Test (DMT) developed by the researchers with 30 multiple choice objective questions with five (5) options to measure students' performance. The items have been designed to evaluate lower cognitive and higher thinking processes. The 30 item multiple choice questions covered the JSS syllabus as demanded by the Mathematics curriculum. The DMT was designed for both pre testing and post-testing of students' cognitive achievement before and after treatment.

Validity of the Instrument

The content validity of the test items was subjected to face validation by the experts from Mathematics education and measurement and evaluation to validate. They critically examined the suitability and appropriateness of the items, the clarity and adequacy of the standard among other things.

Reliability of the Instrument

The instrument was subjected to one of the schools among the study population. While a test-retest reliability was established by using Pearson's product moment correlation formula was used to estimate the reliability. The correlation coefficient of 0.86 was obtained.

Method of Data Collection

Pre-test were administered by the researchers with the help of the research assistants to the two groups before treatment, At the end of the six weeks' treatment, post-tests were also administered to the subjects. Both the pre-test and post-tests serves as data used to compare between the performance of the students, which were also analyzed to answer research questions using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) because they provide summary to describe the basic features of the data collected from the sample and tested the formulated hypotheses using t-test statistics been the most suitable for testing significant differences between the two groups.

Method for Data Analysis

The data generated from the study were analyzed using various statistics. Research questions were answered using mean, standard deviation of test scores. The research hypotheses 1 and 2 were tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test statistics because the mean difference between the two groups (experimental and control) was observed. All these were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20.

RESULTS

The following null hypotheses were tested using t-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance with the aid of SPSS package. Table 1, 2, and 3 were tested using t-test.

HO₁: There is no significant difference in performance between the students with Dyscalculia and normal students in Mathematics in Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto state

To set HO₁, post- test scores of students exposed to treatment were subjected to t-test analysis, summary of the analysis is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of T-test on performance between the students with Dyscalculia and normal students in Mathematics in Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto state

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t-cal.	P-value	Decision
Dyscalculia Students	96	22.14	6.63	3.29	0.00	HO₁: Rejected
Normal Students	245	21.15	7.81			

$\alpha = 0.05$

The results presented in Table 1 shows the t-test analysis of performance of experimental group (Dyscalculia students) and control group (Normal students). From the table, p-value of 0.00 obtained is less than the alpha value of 0.05 (t = 3.29; p-value = 0.00 < 0.05). This indicates that there is significant difference in performance of students taught Mathematics in the experimental group and the students taught Mathematics in the control group in favour of experimental group (Dyscalculia). Thus, the null hypothesis is therefore rejected.

HO₂: There is no significant difference in performance between Male and Female students with Dyscalculia in Mathematics in Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto state

To set HO₂, post- test scores of students with Dyscalculia problems exposed to treatment were subjected to t-test analysis, summary of the analysis is shown in Table 2

Table 2: Summary of T-tests Comparing Male and Female in Experimental Group (Dyscalculia Students)

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t-cal.	p-value	Decision
Male	42	21.36	5.71	1.68	0.96	HO₂: Retained
Female	48	20.13	6.51			

$\alpha = 0.05$

The results presented in Table 2 shows the t-test analysis of performance of male and female in experimental group (Dyscalculia students). From the table, p-value of 0.96 obtained is greater than the alpha value of 0.05 (t = 1.68; p-value = 0.96 > 0.05). This indicates that there is no significant difference in performance of male and female students taught Mathematics in the experimental group (Dyscalculia). Thus, the null hypothesis is therefore retained.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

Research question one results presented revealed that there was difference in the experimental group and control group at pre-test stage considering their mean scores. From the table, the experimental group had a mean score of 21.94 and standard deviation of 5.73. while the control group had a mean score of 20.17 and standard deviation of 6.41 respectively. The mean difference was 1.77. To confirm whether there was a significant difference, the data was further subjected to t-test and the summary of the result presented in Table 1 which shows the t-test analysis of performance of experimental group (Dyscalculia students) and control group (Normal students). From the table, p-value of 0.00 obtained is less than the alpha value of

0.05 ($t = 3.29$; $p\text{-value} = 0.00 < 0.05$). This indicates that there is significant difference in performance of students taught Mathematics in the experimental group and the students taught Mathematics in the control group in favour of experimental group (Dyscalculia). Thus, the null hypothesis is therefore rejected.

These findings lend credence to those from other researchers around the world. For instance, Butterworth, et al. (2011) and Waco, et al. (2011) estimated a prevalence of dyscalculia among students of about 5 to 7% which was almost the same as what Butterworth (2004) had discovered among 6-14-years old students. Another estimate in the UK is at 3% to 6% of the population with dyscalculia (Goldman, 2010c; Wilson, 2012). Doyle (2010) also asserts that worldwide studies estimated the prevalence of dyscalculia within the range 3% to 11% and most likely dyscalculia students perform below average in the Mathematical tests.

Research question two results presented revealed shows the difference between the male and female students with dyscalculia in Mathematics in junior secondary schools in Sokoto state. It revealed that male students in the experimental group had mean score of 22.34 and standard deviation of 6.54 while

their female counterparts had mean scores $\bar{x} = 19.81$ and $SD = 6.89$. The difference in their mean score = 2.53 in favour of female group. The statistical significance of the mean difference would be observed when the corresponding null hypothesis was tested using SPSS.

Findings on Comparison of Dyscalculics and Normal Children The reviewed studies on comparing dyscalculics with normal children are only a few in number (Tishler, 1981). On comparing students with mathematics learning disabilities and students with low mathematics achievement in solving word problems, it was shown that students with low mathematics achievement had more computational errors but fewer translation errors when compared to students with mathematics learning disabilities who had conceptual difficulties in the areas of analyzing, reasoning and abstract thinking (Hartmann & Ann, 2008). A learning disability like dyscalculia is highly prevalent among schoolchildren and has become a serious hindrance in today's educational scenario. Once parents and teachers notice that children have severe problems with arithmetic skills, they can seek help from qualified professionals. By choosing materials and activities suited to their level of learning and by stimulating their urge to bring out their best, teachers can help the pupils with arithmetic learning disabilities to turn their difficulties into special opportunities to be model achievers.

A learning disability like dyscalculia need to be studied intensively to meet the special needs of dyscalculics who need special attention to learn mathematics effectively. Mathematically disabled individuals need special support apart from classroom teaching. They require special help to learn normally through specialized approaches to teaching. So, it is becoming imperative for researchers to conduct surveys and experiments in this area to meet the special needs of dyscalculics who need special attention

CONCLUSION

On the basis of the findings, the instructional methods adopted by the teachers greatly affect the students' learning of the concept. This is reflected in their achievement and acquisition of treatment used for students with dyscalculia problems which enhanced students' performance towards Mathematics in experimental group than those in the control group. It also enhances the advancement of Mathematics education that leads to independent learning and problem solving abilities in both male and female students.

On common areas of mathematics difficulties among students with dyscalculia a majority of junior secondary school's students failed some questions in the mathematical test items. Main common area being mastery of mathematical concept followed by arithmetic difficulties.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study,

To encourage meaningful learning activities, Mathematics educators should emphasize the

implementation of remediation by the use of teacher-centred approach especially areas involving abstract concepts. Active involvement of students in the teaching process, hence the gap between the weak and fast learners in terms of academic performance can arouse and sustain the interest of the students using scientific process skills, the learners will achieve higher and retain more of what is learned. This will equip the students intellectually and lead to a remarkable breakthrough in Mathematics. More precisely:

1. The teaching of Mathematics should be conducted in an effective way in the improvement of dyscalculia students' performance to learn meaningfully and develop positive attitude towards Mathematical concepts. They should therefore be incorporated into the main stream of pedagogy in the teaching of Mathematics at Junior Secondary School levels.
2. The teaching of dyscalculia students should be encouraged from the stake holders in education in teaching mathematics. There should be evaluation process, regular and effective supervision which discourages memorization of facts and principles but which places emphasis on instructional strategies that will help students retain learned Mathematical concepts.
3. The learning of Mathematics should be encouraged to both male and female dyscalculia Junior Secondary School students as well as making sure they pass their examinations effectively.

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